

**RAISING THE SPEECH OF PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS
THROUGH A DICTIONARY OF TERMS IN UZBEK LINGUISTICS**

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Annotation

This article shows the importance of the vocabulary of terms in Uzbek linguistics when growing the speech of Primary School students and the ways and methods of growing the speech of students by introducing terms into the speech of the student.

Keywords: pronoun, pronoun, dictionary, glossary of terms, primary class, speech, speech skills, colloquial konpitence, types of speech.

**РАЗВИТИЕ РЕЧИ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ ЧЕРЕЗ СЛОВАРЬ
ТЕРМИНОВ В УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКОЗНАНИИ**

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Аннотация

В данной статье показано значение словаря терминов в узбекском языкознании для развития речи учащихся начальных классов, а также способы и способы развития речи учащихся путем введения терминов в речь учащихся.

Ключевые слова: термин, терминология, лексика, словарь терминов, начальный класс, речь, речевые навыки, речевой состав, виды речи.

It is known that terminological dictionaries are also very important in the regulation of field terminology. Academician G. Abdurahmanov emphasized that terminology plays an important role in the regulation, improvement and standardization of terms, not only serving a specific field of science. Terminology Choosing terms for dictionaries is a very responsible task. Because each term must correctly express a certain concept in accordance with the field in which it is expressed and at the same time with the laws of the native language. The chosen term should be a single, concise word or combination, and it should not have synonyms. Terminology dictionaries are compiled in one language or in two languages, and its task is to explain and explain the terms in each field. Such dictionaries are also called "Special dictionaries", i.e. "Field dictionaries". Terminology dictionaries are compiled in any field, terms occupy a special place in the lexicon of scientific style.

The signs of the scientific method of terminology are recognized as leading. Modern science and technology is characterized by differentiation and specialization. For example, modern science is divided into more than 500 fields and branches, each of which has its own sophisticated terminology. At the same time, all fields and branches of science and technology are specialized as well as general, therefore, they are not limited to the narrow interests of specialists in the field.

Terminology should be convenient for use in specific practical cases. One of the characteristic features of modern terminology. Disproportionate levels of general public encounter with terms used among narrow specialists. Because science and technology, especially in our country, remains the property of the masses.

Nowadays, it is necessary to know how to build a dictionary, show its similarity, compatibility, and how to achieve it. Its primary importance is processing methods of lexicography.

The most important thing in creating dictionaries is to solve primary problems based on the basic position. Therefore, the above requirements are related to each other: their relationship depends on what kind of research in what concrete reality. Along with theoretical revision, learning in practice has an impact on the structure of vocabulary. The listed requirements serve in the classification of dictionaries. At the same time, there are dictionaries of the level corresponding to one or another requirement.

However, such dictionaries only help students in reading text. Students often realize that certain issues will be discussed in the lesson from their homework, and when they are preparing for it, when they suspect that the meaning of a word is not correct, they want to look up this word in the dictionary. In such cases, foreign language native language dictionaries in textbooks will not help them. Some authors, such as I. E. Anichkov, deny the importance of separate words, he suggests teaching only sentences and oral speech. However, looking at the issue from this point of view, it should be considered that the speech intended for understanding the words that have been isolated at that time should also be taught to express one's opinion. In this case, there will be no need for Russian dictionaries as a foreign language.

The problem of terminology is one of the most complex scientific problems. Not only linguists of various fields, but also experts from various other disciplines can participate in its creation.

Terminology is a word with a definite meaning. As a rule, terminology means the same thing. To be more precise, terminology strives for monosemy (monosemy), the Uzbek language. Theoretical issues of terminology have been separated from practice. As a result, a number of terminological dictionaries of somewhat low quality have been created. In textbooks and training manuals, reference books, as well as in periodicals published in the 70s and 80s, terms that do not meet the requirements of terminology began to be used more often. What

are the main shortcomings of the terminology of the Uzbek language.

In Uzbek languages, there are several types of term formation tools. The most widely used types in terminology are affixal and composition (word addition) methods. By this method, simple artificial and complex (compound) terms are formed.

In terminology, including Uzbek terminology, there are a number of confusions in the orthography of the terminology, the limits of which are not defined, the criteria for their use in terminology are not defined.

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